

THE ROLE OF COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE AS AN EFFORT TO ACTIVATE CREATIVE CENTRES: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY IN PURWAKARTA

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Abstract. The implementation of collaborative governance in managing the creative economy sector has become increasingly essential, particularly at the local level where multiple stakeholders interact. This study explores the role of collaborative government in the activation process of the Creative Center Purwakarta (CCP), a collaborative space established to support creative community activities in Purwakarta, West Java. Employing a qualitative phenomenological approach, the research involved ten key informants, including government officials, CCP managers, members of creative communities, and residents directly engaged in the use of CCP. Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews and document analysis. The findings reveal that although the government has provided facilities and regulatory support, collaboration remains limited to administrative coordination and has yet to fully foster participatory and innovative synergy. Personal engagement strategies, the government's facilitative role, and the ability to adapt to policy changes emerged as key factors driving effective collaboration. The study concludes that the successful activation of CCP requires a dialogic collaborative structure, facilitative leadership, and governance that is responsive to local policy dynamics. These findings offer practical implications for local governments in strengthening creative ecosystems and contribute to the theoretical development of collaborative governance in the creative economy sector.

Keywords: collaborative governance; creative economy; creative center; community participation; local policy

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative governance is a governance approach that emphasises direct involvement between state and non-state actors in collective, deliberative, and consensus-based decision-making processes. This approach is considered capable of addressing difficulties in public policy management, including in the development of the creative economy sector, which requires cross-sector and cross-actor collaboration [1]. However, the implementation of collaborative governance in the local context, particularly in Purwakarta Regency, still faces various challenges. Although a creative centre has been established as a hub for creative economic development and community expression, the reality shows that synergy between the local government through the Purwakarta Regency Tourism, Culture, and Creative Economy Office, managers, and the creative community has not yet been fully optimised [2].

Collaboration, which should be participatory and open to all parties, remains limited to administrative and sectoral approaches. Such conditions result in weak coordination among stakeholders, suboptimal utilisation of creative centre facilities, and a lack of collaborative innovation arising from interactions among actors [3]. When collaboration is ineffective, institutional capacity and public participation

weaken, ultimately impacting the progress of sectors that should be dynamic, such as the creative economy [4]. To address these issues, the application of collaborative governance principles needs to be optimised in the management of creative centres. The success of collaboration is influenced by several factors, such as initial conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership, and interaction processes that build trust and shared commitment [5].

Research on the role of collaborative governance in activating creative centres is important given the need to build strong collaborative networks, optimise the potential of local resources, and create a sustainable and open creative economy ecosystem. This aligns with the importance of exploring the meaning of collective experiences to understand a phenomenon deeply, as well as the success of modern governance, which is greatly influenced by the synergy between various actors in a complex social context [6].

There are several studies relevant to this research problem, such as the study by Musleh et al [7] from Indonesia. Conducting a study on *The Role of Institutional Design and Enabling Environmental: Collaborative Governance of a Pilgrimage Tourism, Indonesia*. Using a qualitative approach in analysing the perspectives of various stakeholders in collaborative governance at tourism sites. The research

context is in Indonesia, with a specific focus on community participation in the management of pilgrimage tourism involving various stakeholders, including local communities as pilgrimage guides. The research findings indicate that collaboration between stakeholders and facilitative leadership are key factors in achieving effective governance. The study also highlights that while there is potential for better collaboration, the roles of the private sector and government remain limited [7].

Research by Mészáros [8] from Romania. Conducted a study on Collaborative Governance for Smart and Sustainable Cities of the 21st Century: Case Study of the City of Oradea. Using a qualitative design with a case study approach to analyse policies and practices implemented in the city of Oradea, Romania. The research context involves various stakeholders, including the city government, the private sector, and the community, to create a governance model that can meet the challenges of urbanisation in the 21st century. In the study, the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with 20 participants consisting of government officials, community representatives, and academics involved in the development of smart city policies in Oradea. The results of the study show that the success of collaborative governance in Oradea is highly dependent on effective communication mechanisms among all parties involved.

Research by Unceta et al [9], conducting a study on Digitalisation of Creative Industries Fostered by Collaborative Governance: Public Innovation Labs in Gipuzkoa. The context of this research includes collaboration between various actors in the creative industry, including local government, private companies, and educational institutions. The participants involved in this research consisted of 15 stakeholders from these sectors, providing a comprehensive overview of the collaborative dynamics occurring in public innovation labs. The research findings indicate that public innovation labs in Gipuzkoa function as an effective platform for facilitating cross-sector collaboration. This study emphasises the importance of community involvement and a collaborative approach in ensuring the success of various digital initiatives designed to modernise the creative industry.

In response to previous studies, such as Musleh et al. [7], which focused solely on community participation in the management of pilgrimage tourism without examining government collaboration with stakeholders in creative centres, and Mészáros [8], which focused solely on the application of collaborative governance in the context of smart and sustainable city development without examining collaborative governance in the context of creative centre activation. Furthermore, the research by Unceta et al [9] only focused on analysing collaboration between the public sector and other stakeholders in developing technology-based creative solutions, without examining government collaboration with stakeholders in activating creative centres. The subsequent research by Li et al [10] only focuses on community-based tourism collaboration that is strongly related to cultural sustainability, without examining the

relationship between government collaboration and tourism through creative centres. Therefore, this research focuses on the role of government collaboration in activating creative centres in Purwakarta, with the aim of answering questions about the role of collaborative governance in these efforts.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative research design with a phenomenological approach to explore in depth the experiences, meanings, and perceptions of the actors involved in government collaboration to activate the Purwakarta Creative Centre [11]. The phenomenological approach was chosen because it is considered most appropriate for understanding subjective realities and the dynamics of collaboration between stakeholders. Participants consisted of ten individuals selected using snowball sampling techniques, including civil servants (ASN), local community members, and the public involved in the activation of the Purwakarta Creative Centre (CCP). Participants from the West Java Provincial Tourism and Culture Office played an important role in the design and utilisation of the CCP. Other participants came from local communities involved in the implementation and management of the CCP, as well as members of the public who had been involved in its activation.

This study began with the identification of issues related to challenges in collaboration among stakeholders in the management of creative economy centres, followed by a literature review to understand the concept of collaborative governance. Data collection techniques used in-depth interviews and document analysis [12], which were analysed thematically to identify patterns of collaborative experiences, challenges, and supporting factors [13]. The research location was at the Purwakarta Creative Centre and the West Java Provincial Tourism and Culture Office, which are hubs for creative communities and play a crucial role in managing the creative economy sector [14]. In-depth interviews were chosen because they provide a broad space for exploring the dynamics of interaction between actors and the context of collaboration in the field [15], [16].

II. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Creative Space as a Means for the Government to Embrace the Community

The need for organised creative spaces in Purwakarta served as a strong foundation for the local government to initiate the Purwakarta Creative Centre (CCP). Prior to the CCP's existence, the creative community tended to be fragmented and lacked a supportive environment for cross-sector collaboration. Within the framework of collaborative governance, the development of the CCP demonstrates the government's active role as an initiator and facilitator in providing social infrastructure that enables community interaction and synergy.

The government's presence, in addition to supporting creative economic development such as CCP, also acts as a

catalyst in overcoming the problem of separation between communities that previously did not work together. CCP has become a gathering point that not only provides physical facilities but also creates a collaborative atmosphere that encourages the exchange of ideas and cross-disciplinary experimentation. This concept aligns with the placemaking approach popularised by Markusen and Gadwa [17], where a place is not merely viewed through its functional aspects but also its role as a social space. This social space then shapes the collective identity resulting from collaboration. In this context, CCP can be seen as part of the effort to build a collective local identity rooted in collaborative creativity.

This demonstrates how the government does not merely act as a regulator but also as an enabler that provides inclusive spaces. This aligns with the concept of networked governance, where physical spaces serve as meeting points for various actors in co-creating ideas and programmes, in line with Malpass et al.'s [18] perspective on the importance of collaborative spaces in strengthening community-based creative economies.

B. Personal Approach as an Initial Collaborative Strategy

The initial process of activating the CCP is marked by a personal approach taken by managers towards the community. In collaborative governance practices, this reflects efforts to build trust-building mechanisms, namely by strengthening interpersonal relationships before forming formal cooperation structures.

Managers visit communities one by one, explain the benefits of the CCP, and open two-way communication channels. This strategy shows that collaboration does not always start with formal policies, but rather with social relations that enable organic participation. The emphasis on informal communication is also in line with the soft governance model proposed by Schöfer et al. [19], in which trust, and reciprocal relationships form the foundation for active community involvement.

This strategy is not commonly used in bureaucratic circles, but it is precisely what makes CCP so powerful. In this case, the managers conduct a kind of informal community mapping, making the community feel involved from the outset. This approach demonstrates the importance of co-design in public policymaking, where the community is not positioned as the object of the programme but also as a subject that participates in its design. Ultimately, the community will feel that the programme is part of the community. This approach is like that taken by several creative urban initiatives, such as Hackney Wick in London, where local actors are given space to design their own ecosystem [20].

C. The Government's Role as a Facilitator of Collaboration, Not Just a Provider of Resources

Government support in the context of CCP is not limited to funding but is more strongly evident in the provision of facilities, regulatory ease, and the creation of open dialogue spaces. In the logic of collaborative governance, this demonstrates the government's role as a facilitator that conditions the ecosystem so that collaboration between actors can grow healthily.

Although budget constraints are recognised as an obstacle, the government continues to contribute through administrative support and the provision of legal space that allows communities to operate. This is in line with the findings of Gasparin & Quinn [21], which show that creative ecosystems can thrive without direct financial support, as long as there is institutional and regulatory support that allows creative actors to operate and collaborate effectively.

D. Managers' Adaptation to Regional Policy Dynamics

Within the framework of collaborative governance, CCP managers are not subordinate to the government but rather partners who must be adaptive to policy changes resulting from local political dynamics. Changes in leadership and new regulations require managers to re-adjust programme planning processes to remain aligned with current regulations.

This pattern highlights the importance of flexible and dialogic governance in managing collaborative public facilities. This aligns with Janssen & Voort's [22] view on the need for adaptive and responsive governance that can adapt to policy changes and dynamic conditions to ensure the sustainability of public services despite power transitions.

E. Synergy Among Actors as the Cornerstone of Collaborative Governance

The success of CCP is inseparable from strong communication and synergy among stakeholders. Discussion forums, joint evaluations, and spaces for expressing criticism and suggestions are integral components of collaborative governance practices that prioritise transparency, accountability, and active participation. The government, managers, and community play complementary roles. The government acts as a facilitator, managers as connectors, and the community as the primary drivers of activities. In line with the findings of Zhang et al. [23], the success of collaboration depends on how all actors understand their respective roles in achieving objectives, and the importance of collaborative governance in managing sustainable creative programmes is emphasised.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This study examines the role of collaborative governance in activating the Purwakarta Creative Centre (CCP) as a shared space for creative communities. The findings show that collaboration between actors, the government, managers, and communities—plays a crucial role in realising a participatory and sustainable creative ecosystem. The government, through the Purwakarta Regency Tourism, Culture, and Creative Economy Office, has endeavoured to act as a facilitator by providing facilities, streamlined regulations, and open communication channels, although budget constraints remain a significant obstacle. The personalised approach adopted by managers in engaging with the community highlights that social trust serves as the foundational basis for collaboration. Additionally, the dynamics of local policies require CCP management to adopt an adaptive stance to remain relevant amid shifts in government direction. However, ideal collaboration remains

hindered by sectoral coordination patterns, weak community-based innovation, and the absence of a structured collaborative governance system. Overall, this study affirms that collaborative governance is not merely an administrative strategy but an institutional approach requiring facilitative leadership, dialogic interaction structures, and clarity of roles among stakeholders. Activating creative spaces like CCPs necessitates adaptive policy support, regulatory sustainability, and consistent vision across governments.

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